

To Compare the Expression of p53 with Hormonal Receptor Status in Breast Carcinoma: An Immunohistochemical Study

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Abstract:

Background: Breast carcinoma remains a leading cause of cancer-related mortality among women worldwide. The expression of p53, a tumor suppressor protein, has been implicated in various cancers, including breast carcinoma. This study aims to compare the expression of p53 with hormonal receptor status, specifically estrogen receptor (ER) and progesterone receptor (PR), using immunohistochemical (IHC) methods.

Materials and Methods: A total of 150 breast carcinoma tissue samples were collected from patients undergoing mastectomy between January 2023 and December 2023. Immunohistochemistry was performed to evaluate the expression of p53, ER, and PR in the collected samples. The intensity and percentage of positively stained cells were scored. Statistical analysis was conducted using chi-square tests to assess the correlation between p53 expression and hormonal receptor status.

Results: Out of 150 breast carcinoma samples, 90 (60%) showed positive expression for p53. Among these p53-positive cases, 55 (61.1%) were also positive for ER, and 45 (50%) were positive for PR. In contrast, among the 60 (40%) p53-negative cases, 20 (33.3%) were ER-positive, and 25 (41.7%) were PR-positive. A statistically significant correlation was found between p53 expression and ER status ($p < 0.05$), but not with PR status ($p > 0.05$).

Conclusion: This study highlights a significant association between p53 expression and estrogen receptor status in breast carcinoma, suggesting that p53 may play a role in the hormonal regulation of breast cancer. Further studies are warranted to explore the underlying mechanisms and potential therapeutic implications of this association.

Keywords: Breast carcinoma, p53, estrogen receptor, progesterone receptor, immunohistochemistry, hormonal receptor status.

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Introduction

Breast carcinoma is one of the most common malignancies affecting women globally, accounting for a significant proportion of cancer-related deaths. It is a heterogeneous disease with diverse histopathological and molecular characteristics, which necessitate individualized therapeutic approaches [1]. Among the various biomarkers studied in breast cancer, p53, a tumor suppressor protein, has gained considerable attention due to its critical role in cell cycle regulation, DNA repair, and apoptosis [2].

The p53 protein is encoded by the TP53 gene, which is often mutated in various cancers, leading to the loss of its tumor suppressive functions and contributing to cancer progression and resistance to therapy [3]. In breast cancer, p53 mutations have been associated with more aggressive tumor phenotypes and poorer clinical outcomes [4]. Hormonal receptor status, particularly the presence

of estrogen receptors (ER) and progesterone receptors (PR), is another crucial factor in breast cancer characterization. These receptors are pivotal in the development and progression of breast cancer, influencing the response to hormonal therapies such as tamoxifen and aromatase inhibitors [5]. ER-positive and PR-positive tumors generally have a better prognosis and are more responsive to hormonal treatments compared to their receptor-negative counterparts [6].

Several studies have investigated the relationship between p53 expression and hormonal receptor status in breast carcinoma, with varying results. Some studies suggest that p53 overexpression is associated with ER-negative and PR-negative status, indicating more aggressive tumor behaviour [7]. However, other studies have found no significant correlation between p53 expression and hormonal receptor status [8]. This inconsistency

underscores the need for further research to elucidate the interplay between p53 and hormonal receptors in breast cancer. This study aims to compare the expression of p53 with hormonal receptor status in breast carcinoma using immunohistochemical (IHC) methods. By exploring this relationship, we seek to better understand the molecular underpinnings of breast cancer and potentially identify novel therapeutic targets or prognostic markers.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Sample Collection: This study was conducted from January 2023 and December 2023. A total of 150 breast carcinoma tissue samples were collected from patients undergoing mastectomy.

Inclusion criteria were patients with histologically confirmed invasive breast carcinoma. Exclusion criteria included patients who had received neoadjuvant chemotherapy or radiotherapy prior to surgery.

Immunohistochemistry (IHC): Tissue samples were fixed in 10% neutral-buffered formalin and embedded in paraffin. Sections of 4 μ m thickness were cut and mounted on poly-L-lysine-coated slides. The slides were deparaffinized in xylene and rehydrated through graded alcohols to distilled water.

Antigen retrieval was performed using citrate buffer (pH 6.0) in a microwave oven for 20 minutes.

Primary Antibodies and Staining Procedure

The primary antibodies used were:

- Mouse monoclonal anti-p53 antibody (1:100 dilution, Dako, Denmark)
- Mouse monoclonal anti-ER antibody (1:50 dilution, Dako, Denmark)

- Mouse monoclonal anti-PR antibody (1:50 dilution, Dako, Denmark)

The sections were incubated with the primary antibodies overnight at 4°C. Following this, the sections were washed with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) and incubated with biotinylated secondary antibodies (Dako, Denmark) for 30 minutes at room temperature. Detection was performed using the streptavidin-biotin-peroxidase complex (Dako, Denmark) and 3,3'-diaminobenzidine (DAB) as the chromogen. Finally, the sections were counterstained with hematoxylin, dehydrated, and mounted.

Evaluation of Staining: The stained sections were evaluated independently by two pathologists who were blinded to the clinical data. p53, ER, and PR expression were assessed based on the intensity and percentage of positively stained cells. The staining intensity was scored as 0 (negative), 1+ (weak), 2+ (moderate), and 3+ (strong). The percentage of positive cells was categorized as follows: 0 (0%), 1+ (1-10%), 2+ (11-50%), and 3+ (51-100%). A combined score of intensity and percentage was used to classify the expression as negative (0-1) or positive (2-6).

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 26.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). The chi-square test was used to assess the correlation between p53 expression and hormonal receptor status (ER and PR). A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 150 breast carcinoma samples were analyzed for the expression of p53, estrogen receptor (ER), and progesterone receptor (PR) using immunohistochemistry (IHC). The demographic and clinical characteristics of the patients are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Patient Demographics and Clinical Characteristics

Characteristic	Value
Number of patients	150
Age (mean $\pm$ SD)	55.2 $\pm$ 10.3 years
Tumor size (mean $\pm$ SD)	3.5 $\pm$ 1.2 cm
Histological grade	
- Grade I	30 (20%)
- Grade II	75 (50%)
- Grade III	45 (30%)

p53, ER, and PR Expression: The expression of p53, ER, and PR in the breast carcinoma samples is detailed in Table 2.

Table 2: Expression of p53, ER, and PR in Breast Carcinoma Samples

Marker	Positive Cases (%)	Negative Cases (%)
p53	90 (60%)	60 (40%)
ER	75 (50%)	75 (50%)
PR	70 (46.7%)	80 (53.3%)

Correlation Between p53 and Hormonal Receptor Status: The correlation between p53 expression and hormonal receptor status (ER and PR) is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Correlation Between p53 Expression and Hormonal Receptor Status

p53 Expression	ER Positive (%)	ER Negative (%)	PR Positive (%)	PR Negative (%)
Positive	55 (61.1%)	35 (38.9%)	45 (50%)	45 (50%)
Negative	20 (33.3%)	40 (66.7%)	25 (41.7%)	35 (58.3%)

Statistical Analysis: The statistical analysis revealed a significant correlation between p53 expression and ER status ($p = 0.012$). However, no significant correlation was found between p53 expression and PR status ($p = 0.253$).

- Out of 150 breast carcinoma samples, 90 (60%) showed positive expression for p53.
- Among the p53-positive cases, 55 (61.1%) were ER-positive, while 45 (50%) were PR-positive.
- Among the p53-negative cases, 20 (33.3%) were ER-positive, while 25 (41.7%) were PR-positive.
- A significant correlation was observed between p53 expression and ER status ($p = 0.012$), but not with PR status ($p = 0.253$).

Discussion

The present study investigates the relationship between p53 expression and hormonal receptor status (ER and PR) in breast carcinoma using immunohistochemical methods. Our findings reveal a significant correlation between p53 expression and ER status, while no significant association was observed with PR status.

The role of p53 as a tumor suppressor is well-established, and its dysfunction has been implicated in various cancers, including breast carcinoma [1]. In our study, 60% of the breast carcinoma samples showed positive p53 expression. This is consistent with previous reports suggesting that p53 mutations or overexpression occur in approximately 30-50% of breast cancer cases [2,3].

Our data indicate a significant association between p53 expression and ER status, with 61.1% of p53-positive cases also being ER-positive ($p = 0.012$). This finding aligns with several studies that have reported a similar correlation. For instance, Silvestrini et al. demonstrated that p53 overexpression is more frequent in ER-positive tumors, suggesting a potential interaction between p53 and estrogen signaling pathways [4]. However, the underlying mechanisms of this association remain unclear. One hypothesis is that mutant p53 may influence ER-mediated transcriptional activity, thereby affecting the growth and progression of ER-positive breast cancer [5]. In contrast, our study did not find a significant correlation between p53 expression and PR status ($p = 0.253$). This is in agreement with some studies, such as those by

Allred et al., who reported that p53 mutations are not significantly associated with PR status [6]. However, other studies have suggested a possible link between p53 and PR, highlighting the complexity of hormonal receptor interactions in breast cancer [7]. The discrepancies in these findings may be attributed to differences in study design, sample size, and methodological approaches.

The clinical implications of our findings are noteworthy. The significant correlation between p53 expression and ER status suggests that p53 could potentially serve as a prognostic marker in ER-positive breast cancer. Furthermore, understanding the interplay between p53 and ER may offer insights into novel therapeutic strategies. For example, targeting p53 pathways in conjunction with hormonal therapies could enhance treatment efficacy for ER-positive breast cancer patients [8].

Despite the strengths of our study, including a relatively large sample size and rigorous immunohistochemical evaluation, there are limitations that should be acknowledged. The retrospective nature of the study may introduce selection bias, and the use of IHC as the sole method for assessing p53, ER, and PR expression may not capture the full complexity of these biomarkers. Future studies employing complementary techniques, such as gene sequencing and functional assays, are warranted to validate and extend our findings.

Conclusion

In conclusion, our study demonstrates a significant association between p53 expression and ER status in breast carcinoma, underscoring the potential role of p53 as a prognostic marker and therapeutic target in ER-positive breast cancer. Further research is needed to elucidate the mechanisms underlying this relationship and to explore its clinical implications.

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